

Building connections: enhancing LinkedIn presence for third space women

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As third space educators, we navigate the complex intersection of professional and academic roles, which often lacks clear career progression pathways compared to traditional academia. Women are disproportionately represented in third space roles but remain underrepresented in senior leadership positions. This can lead to feelings of isolation, particularly in the increasingly remote working environment. Simultaneously, the rapid evolution of higher education, technology, and diverse student needs demands continual professional development. Through interactive discussions and feedback, we aimed to co-create a tailored approach to using LinkedIn as a tool for career advancement in the third space, addressing challenges unique to women in leadership. Participants' insights were invaluable in refining these strategies to support leadership growth among third space professionals who are women.

Reflection

We ran an interactive 30-minute workshop going through each of four implications (Building your LinkedIn brand; Networking for success; Managing imposter syndrome; and Content strategy development) from our ASCILITE poster. We had engaging discussions with like-minded workshop attendees. The main take-away from the exercise was that there are limited resources on career guidance for women in third space professions, which provoked us to create and enhance the Leadership Identity Framework for Transformation (LIFT) framework.

References

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